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GreenCharge Project Deliverable: D8.6

High Impact Communication Report

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About GreenCharge

GreenCharge takes us a few important steps closer to achieving one of the dreams of modern cities: a zero-emission transport system based on electric vehicles running on green energy, with traffic jams and parking problems becoming things of the past. The project promotes:

Power to the people! The GreenCharge dream can only be achieved if people feel confident that they can access charging infrastructure as and when they need it. So GreenCharge is developing a smart charging system that lets people book charging in advance, so that they can easily access the power they need.

The delicate balance of power If lots of people try to charge their vehicles around the same time (e.g. on returning home from work), public electricity suppliers may struggle to cope with the peaks in demand. So we are developing software for automatic energy management in local areas to balance demand with available supplies. This balancing act combines public supplies and locally produced reusable energy, using local storage as a buffer and staggering the times at which vehicles get charged.

Getting the financial incentives right Electric motors may make the wheels go round, but money makes the world go round. So we are devising and testing business models that encourage use of electric vehicles and sharing of energy resources, allowing all those involved to cooperate in an economically viable way.

Showing how it works in practice GreenCharge is testing all of these innovations in practical trials in Barcelona, Bremen and Oslo. Together, these trials cover a wide variety of factors: *vehicle type* (scooters, cars, buses), *ownership model* (private, shared individual use, public transport), *charging locations* (private residences, workplaces, public spaces, transport hubs), *energy management* (using solar power, load balancing at one charging station or within a neighbourhood, battery swapping), and *charging support* (booking, priority charging).

To help cities and municipalities make the transition to zero emission/sustainable mobility, the project is producing three main sets of results: (1) *innovative business models*; (2) *technological support*; and (3) *guidelines* for cost efficient and successful deployment and operation of charging infrastructure for Electric Vehicles (EVs).

The *innovative business models* are inspired by ideas from the sharing economy, meaning they will show how to use and share the excess capacity of private renewable energy sources (RES), private charging facilities and the batteries of parked EVs in ways that benefit all involved, financially and otherwise.

The *technological support* will coordinate the power demand of charging with other local demand and local RES, leveraging load flexibility and storage capacity of local stationary batteries and parked EVs. It will also provide user friendly charge planning, booking and billing services for EV users. This will reduce the need for grid investments, address range/charge anxiety and enable sharing of already existing charging facilities for EV fleets.

The *guidelines* will integrate the experience from the trials and simulations and provide advice on localisation of charging points, grid investment reductions, and policy and public communication measures for accelerating uptake of electromobility.

For more information

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Executive Summary

This reports outlines D8.6 High Impact Communication of the GreenCharge project and covers the main results of the communication activities that were executed during the project. At the beginning of the project, these activities were defined in the D8.1. Communication Strategy and plan. This plan defined quantitative and qualitative targets to assess and measure communication impact. This deliverable explains the results of the targets.

This deliverable reports on the impact of GreenCharge's main communication activities. Focus is on high impact communication and covers website, social media, newsletters and publications, conferences, workshops, lectures to students and animation. As such it gives not only a valuable overview of how GreenCharge results have been communicated, but also presents their impact on interested stakeholders. Evaluation of Communication activities is also reported.

The deliverable describes the results of the GreenCharge project, which was shared with the public and the stakeholder groups the consortium. All communication actions were realised with the purpose to achieve these following goals:

- **Establishing the GreenCharge “Brand” within the EU:** It concerns not a brand in the sense of a consumer product, but rather a widely-known “household name” associated with a widely-supported positive goal. The GreenCharge brand could act as a reference for smart charging and Energy Smart Neighbourhoods (ESNs) in the European Union.
- **Synchronisation with EC Communication Activities:** To co-operate actively in events and initiatives organised by the European Commission for promotion of H2020 activities. The goal is to become a highly visible showcase project for H2020.
- **High public visibility:** While GreenCharge addresses specialist and technical audiences, there will also be a major emphasis on addressing policy makers and cities.
- **Political inspiration by leading examples:** GreenCharge aims to provide an easy to reference political example supported by implementing objectives of the EU Transport White Paper and the Urban Mobility Package (SUMP).
- **Increased reputation of EU funded projects:** The aim of the communication strategy is to reach out to society as a whole, while demonstrating how EU funding is used to tackle societal challenges while generating business for (local) entrepreneurs. GreenCharge establishes these goals by publications and seeking media attention. GreenCharge uses several communication channels for reaching out different stakeholder groups, including citizens.

This deliverable is of interest to all communication colleagues on the GreenCharge project and to its sister H2020 projects, to demonstrator city and uptake city representatives and to EU and EU agency staff and the wider H2020 EV Charging community. The deliverable helps them to identify impact of the communication activities on interested stakeholders and provide a basis for developing communication activities on other similar projects, but also in other GreenCharge project activities such as the demos and their further exploitation.

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List of Abbreviations

Table 1: List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CP	Charging Point
CPO	Charging Point Operator
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
eMobility	Electric Mobility
ESN	Energy Smart Neighbourhoods
EU	European Union
EV	Electrical Vehicle
FV	Fossil Fuelled Vehicle
H2020	Horizon 2020
HIC	High Impact Communication
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Milestone
OEM	Original Equipment manufacturers
RDI	Research, development and innovation
SUMP	Sustainable Urban Mobility Planning
V2G	Vehicle to grid
WP	Work Package

1 About this Deliverable

1.1 Why would I want to read this deliverable?

This deliverable reports on the impact of GreenCharge’s main communication activities. Focus is on high impact communication and covers website, social media, newsletters and publications, conferences, workshops, lectures to students and animation. As such it gives not only a valuable overview of how GreenCharge results have been communicated, but also presents their impact on interested stakeholders. Evaluation of communication activities is also reported.

1.2 Intended readership/users

This deliverable is of interest to all communication colleagues on the GreenCharge project and to its sister H2020 projects, to demonstrator city and uptake city representatives and to EU and EU agency staff and the wider H2020 EV Charging community. The deliverable helps them to identify impact of the communication activities on interested stakeholders and provide a basis for developing communication activities on other similar projects, but also in other GreenCharge project activities such as the demos and their further exploitation.

1.3 Other project deliverables that may be of interest

All Communication related deliverables from WP8 and WP1, 2, 3, 5 and 7 (see Table 2 below).

Table 2: Communication related deliverables

Work Package	Deliverable Name	Connection with communication
1 Project and Innovation Management	D1.3 Innovation News & Updates	This deliverable gave an overview on website of new initiatives, new research results, new products and new user needs that were of relevance to eMobility.
2 Pilots in Living Labs	D2.21 Final Report for Barcelona Pilot Lessons Learned and Guidelines D2.15 Final Report for Bremen Pilot Lessons Learned and Guidelines D2.8 Final Report for Oslo Pilot Lessons Learned and Guidelines	These deliverables gave an overview of the three pilots, including the implementation, operation, the tests carried out, services and the data collected. Moreover, it described the lessons learned and guidelines for apartment buildings.
3 Business Model Design and Prototyping	D3.1 Stakeholder Analysis Report	This deliverable gave an overview of an stakeholder analysis, identifying the concerns and needs from all stakeholders relevant for GreenCharge.
5 Innovation Effects Evaluation	D5.1 : Evaluation Design D5.4 : Intermediate Result for Innovation Effects Evaluation D5.5 : Final Result for Innovation Effects Evaluation D5.6 : Open Research Data	D5.1 described the evaluation methodology and schedule including data collection plan. It included the requirement analysis and architecture design of evaluation tools and methods. D5.4 described evaluation results and lessons learned from 1 st iteration evaluation of the integrated technical solution and business models effects, both from field trials on the three pilots and from simulations. D5.5 described the final evaluation results and lessons learned from evaluation of the integrated technical solution and business models effects, both from field trials on the three pilots and from simulations. D5.6 described the data collected from the pilots and structured for further research on the effects of eMobility in cities.

<p>7 eMobility in SUMP</p>	<p>D7.1: GreenCharge SUMP eMobility Approach</p> <p>D7.2 Recommendations and Guidelines for Integrating Electric Mobility into SUMPs</p> <p>D7.3 : Lessons Learned from Roadmap Development in Uptake Cities</p> <p>D7.4 : European Workshop e-mobility and SUMP</p>	<p>D7.1 described the GreenCharge approach to integrating eMobility into SUMP.</p> <p>D7.2 described recommendations and guidelines for integration of eMobility and SUMPs, including innovative carsharing ,new housing developments and ITS concepts. .</p> <p>D7.3 Described the lessons learned from assisting the Uptake cities developing their individual roadmaps for integrating Mobility into SUMPs.</p> <p>D7.4 described the SUMP demonstrator within GreenCharge and to discuss/conclude the guidelines.</p>
<p>8 Maximisation of Impact</p>	<p>D8.1 Communication Plan</p> <p>D8.2 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan</p> <p>D8.3 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (V2)</p> <p>D8.4 Newsletters</p> <p>D8.5 Viable Business and Replication Plans</p> <p>D8.6 High Impact Communication Report</p>	<p>D8.1 described target audiences and the key messages for /type of engagement needed with each group. Moreover, it defines different channels and mechanisms to be used for communication.</p> <p>D8.2 described updated and confirmed plans for the dissemination and exploitation of results and the completed and planned communication activities</p> <p>D8.3 described updated and confirmed plans for the dissemination and exploitation of results and the completed and planned communication activities.</p> <p>D8.4 described valuable archive of condensed information describing, in an easy-to-read and public-facing manner, project activities and the achievement of key project milestones via a series of GreenCharge newsletters</p> <p>D8.5 identified the most viable business models related to electric mobility as identified by GreenCharge and provide initial strategies and plans for replication. Replication was only possible when the information is shared correctly through communication.</p>

1.4 To Other projects and initiatives

GreenCharge cooperated with other projects and initiatives to intensify the communication range. GreenCharge used the relationships among all partners, especially with ICLEI, clustering with other Research Development and Innovation (RDI) projects, the *CIVITAS Initiative*¹, *Uptake Cities Group* and local reference groups, as follows:

- **Relationships with project partner ICLEI:** GreenCharge, through ICLEI, established communication partnerships with existing and relevant projects, stakeholder communities and networks. These pre-existing groups (such as CIVITAS or the Informed Cities group) already had the necessary communication infrastructure in place and therefore helped the project to quickly reach the targeted audiences.
- **Clustering with other RDI projects:** The project liaised with its H2020 sister project MEISTER and other initiatives at a European level (CIVITAS, Informed Cities Forum, EUSEW) and exchanged results and knowledge with each other.
- **The CIVITAS Initiative:** The project liaised with the *CIVITAS Initiative* by joining thematic CIVITAS platforms and using their channels for dissemination. The project promoted and shared the project's lessons and conclusions with cities both inside and outside of the consortium. GreenCharge cooperated with the CIVITAS-secretariat and participated in their lead activities, in particular the CIVITAS SATELLITE, the Coordination and Support Action, which supported the CIVITAS Initiative.

¹ <https://civitas.eu/>

- ***Uptake Cities Group***: Intensive exchange between the 3 pilot cities and the 9 Uptake Cities generated peer-to-peer feedback and added value to the new business models developed for each city and gave input to the roadmaps for replication developed by the 9 Uptake Cities².
- ***Local Reference Groups***: Local Reference Groups were established at the beginning of the project, involving representatives from relevant associations, councils, and other entities/alliances that represent relevant businesses who were potential adopters. These groups were consulted regularly to provide feedback from a user's perspective.

² <https://www.greencharge2020.eu/uptake-cities-group/>

2 Communication in GreenCharge

The development of the High Impact Communication (HIC) report has been part of WP8 – “Maximisation of Impact”. The overall objective of the communication activities has been to broadly inform targeted audiences about the project. Therefore, it was necessary to build and maintain an effective communication within the project and ensured large spreading of the project results to the industry community, the scientific community, policy makers and the broad public.

This specific deliverable describes the HIC-report/output regarding the communication of GreenCharge’s objectives, activities, results, and the involved project partners. The goal of the report is to ensure that the project’s content and outcomes will be widespread to the targeted stakeholders, at appropriate times and based on an appropriate methodology. These activities have been carried out through the whole execution of the project (M1-M42). The HIC-report serves as an impact measurement for any media and public relations activity in which the consortium is engaged.

2.1 Communication Strategy

The communication strategy defined what the consortium wished to share with the public and the stakeholder groups the consortium will reach. All communication actions have been realised with the purpose to achieve these project goals:

- Establishing the GreenCharge “Brand” within the EU: It concerns not a brand in the sense of a consumer product, but rather a widely-known “household name” associated with a widely-supported positive goal. The GreenCharge brand could act as a reference for smart charging and Energy Smart Neighbourhoods (ESNs) in the European Union.
- Synchronisation with EC Communication Activities: To co-operate actively in events and initiatives organised by the European Commission for promotion of H2020 activities. The goal is to become a highly visible showcase project for H2020.
- High public visibility: While GreenCharge will of course address specialist and technical audiences, there will also be a major emphasis on addressing policy makers and cities.
- Political inspiration by leading examples: GreenCharge aims to provide an easy to reference political example supported by implementing objectives of the EU Transport White Paper and the Urban Mobility Package (SUMP).
- Increased reputation of EU funded projects: The aim of the communication strategy is to reach out to society as a whole, while demonstrating how EU funding is used to tackle societal challenges while generating business for (local) entrepreneurs. GreenCharge will establish these goals by publications and seeking media attention. GreenCharge will use several communication channels for reaching out different stakeholder groups, including citizens.

The GreenCharge communication strategy contemplates:

- Specific communication tools that have been developed (i.e. website, press release, newsletters, etc.) with clear responsibilities attributed to each partner.
- Communication measures that have been adopted (i.e. identification of industrial workshops, conferences to be attended, etc.).
- Target audiences have been communicated the project results.

As in all projects, communication in GreenCharge has been about promoting the project itself. But communication also has a second and critical double role: to positively influence the acceptance of eMobility, smart charging and Energy Smart Neighbourhoods (ESN). The communication strategy focused on contacting, informing and engaging different stakeholder groups, based on the outcomes of the stakeholder analysis. Diverse information regimes have been applied to different stakeholders, based on the importance they have for the project and their interest in the outcomes of GreenCharge as derived from the stakeholder analysis. The identified stakeholder groups with a different interest on the project were:

- Cooperative housing associations and other building owners
- Electric Vehicles (EV) drivers/owners/fleet operators
- Smart grid providers
- Charging operators
- Cities & policy makers
- Original Equipment manufacturers (OEM) along the EVs value chain
- Citizens

The communication strategy was built on the prioritization of certain groups of stakeholders. This was initially decided by the consortium, which based on their joint competences decided what external stakeholders were really needed. The stakeholder analysis complements this prioritization by gathering information from all relevant stakeholders, among others by assessing their interest and influence on the project.

At the beginning of GreenCharge, there was only generic news to shared and communicated. It focused mainly on making stakeholders aware of the new EV project. At the beginning, GreenCharge deployed generic communication channels, like the website and periodic newsletters with generic information about the project. As GreenCharge progressed, the project results became more available and more insights were obtained. The information that became available provided the opportunity to involve external stakeholders into the project by changing their perceived interest and attitude with targeted information. The communication measures deployed thus depended on the position a stakeholder had towards the project.

2.1.1 Internal communication

There were two ways of communication throughout the project. Firstly, there was internal/central communication and secondly there was external communication. Both depend on the type of partner that were involved around the project.

Internal communication. Internal communication was the communication among the consortium partners and communication between the consortium as a whole and the EU. The communication between the consortium and the EU would go through the coordinator and the EU project officer.

2.1.2 External (Pilot) communication

External communication. External communication was the communication with people or organisations outside the consortium. For the external communication every project member followed the description below to be in line with the EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement.

According to the Grant Agreement “Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text:

For communication activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 769016”.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results:

“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 769016”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem (see **Figure 2-1**) must have an appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries used the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This did not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.”

As the GreenCharge project members acknowledged and shared the CIVITAS objectives, the cooperation showed in displaying the CIVITAS logo (see **Figure 2-2**) next to the EU emblem.

Both logos have been published on all of the communication materials of the project. This included the deliverables and communication materials (such as brochures and roll-ups) and on presentation templates. The EU logo was always displayed in first place and should not be displayed smaller than the CIVITAS logo.

Figure 2-1: EU emblem³ Figure 2-2: CIVITAS logo

The EU emblem and the CIVITAS logos have been stored on the document management system of the project, as well as all communication material produced.

2.1.3 Target audiences and key messages

GreenCharge has had a very broad “audience”. The messages GreenCharge wanted to transmit, or type of engagement we sought, were different for each type of audience. The table below provides a summary – but keep in mind that the same message can sometimes be of interest to multiple audiences.

Table 3: Target audience of GreenCharge

Target Audience	Message to transmit/Type of Engagement desired
Cooperative housing associations Other building owners	- Charging points can be established with existing grid capacity - ESN solutions save money and environment
EV drivers/owners	Charge bookings/demand registrations is good for environment and good for your economy - Charge booking and eRoaming ease the use of EVs and no "charge anxiety"
Smart grid providers	- ESNs is a market opportunity
Cities	- The potential of ESNs facilitates more charging points and deserves attention - SUMP must include plans for charging infrastructure
Charging operators	- Booking supports load balancing
OEMs	- Vehicle to grid (V2G) to be an advantage to ESNs and indirectly promote EVs
Citizens	As a prosumer, you earn money according to business models - As a citizen, you improve the quality of life: less pollutants, less noise

³ Different formats of the emblems are available here: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

GreenCharge audience went from stakeholders in three defined value chains (see below) over academic institutions, cities and policy makers to the public/society in general. The messages transmitted, or type of engagement sought, were different for each type of audience.

Figure 2-3: The GreenCharge value chains

The main target audiences selected by the consortium, to which the project communicated about the GreenCharge project, the communication pathways and channels for each one are summarized in Table 3 and their key messages in Deliverable D8.1: Communication Strategy and Plan.

2.1.4 Adjustments in strategy

The pandemic affected the GreenCharge project, because it was not possible to have physical events anymore (social distancing). Most of the activities went through digital solutions (for example webinars instead of physical presentations).

2.2 Communication targets

2.2.1 Initial communication targets

This section describes which initial communication targets were developed by Work package 8 (WP8):

- To maximise the impact of the GreenCharge project outcomes within and beyond its lifespan;
- To transfer the project results to relevant stakeholders including policy makers, industry, and society via a systematic communication strategy so that lessons learned from the pilots have a major impact in helping decision makers throughout Europe;
- To make sure that the technologies and business models developed in the project, and the lessons learned from the pilots, are made widely known and available to all relevant stakeholders;
- To facilitate effective project internal and external communication.

According to the European Commission (EC) participant portal website⁴, the term communication is defined as follows:

⁴ European Commission participant portal, <http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal>

Communication: Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

2.2.2 Initial key performance indicators

D8.1 Communication Strategy and Plan defined quantitative and qualitative targets to assess and measure communication impact. Table 4 shows the initial summary of the KPIs and their targets of the GreenCharge project.

Table 4: Initial KPIs Communication Strategy and Plan

Tools	KPI	Expected results	Means of verification
Website	Number of unique visits	3,000	Google analytics
	Number of registered for upload	500	Google analytics
	Number of downloads of content	200	Google analytics
	Number of subscribers for the newsletter	200	Communication report in D8.2
Press coverage	Number of EU wide press releases	8	Copies of press releases
	Number of slots/articles	12	Copies of slots/articles
Publications	Number of newsletters	6	Copies of newsletters
	Number of scientific/technical publications	6	Copies of scientific/technical publications
	Number of brochures spreaded	300	Copies of brochures
Twitter	Number of Tweets	200	Twitter analytics
	Number of followers	200	Twitter analytics
	Number of retweets	50	Twitter analytics
LinkedIn	Number of followers	200	LinkedIn analytics
	Number of unique visits	200	LinkedIn analytics
	Number of posts	18	LinkedIn analytics
YouTube	Number of project videos	1	Records of project videos
	Number of webinars	3	Records of webinars
	Number of views	500	Youtube analytics
	Number of subscribers	50	Youtube analytics
Networks	Number of uptake cities	12	Communication report in D8.2
	Number of reference groups	3	Communication report in D8.2
	Number of actors accessible through partner networks	469	Communication report in D8.2
Events	Number of large-scale events	1	Records of attendance, presentations
	Number of workshops	9	Report of workshops
	Number of open days	3	Records of attendance, presentations
	Number of conferences	20	Records of attendance, presentations

2.2.3 Adjusted targets

The COVID-19 pandemic affected the implementation of the GreenCharge demonstrators and their communication activities, especially the physical events were affected. At the time of outbreak of the pandemic, it was anticipated that the delays could be recovered within the original time frame of the project, but due to subsequent and closer analysis of the continued impact of the outbreak on the project progress had revealed the GreenCharge needed a 6 months' extension. This also had implications on the production of data and lack of data, which resulted in less (scientific) publications.

However, most of the communication activities still took place through digital solutions that GreenCharge embraced. This means that activities as discussed in Table 4 still took place through various digital channels (e.g. YouTube/Microsoft Teams/Zoom and other digital tools).

2.3 Summary table

The summary table (Table 5) can be used for quick and easy reference of the objectives and targets and activities to lead into chapter 3.

Table 5: Summary Table of Objectives, targets, and activities of High Impact Communication

Objectives	Communication Targets	Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing the GreenCharge “Brand” within the EU. The GreenCharge brand could act as a reference for smart charging and Energy Smart Neighbourhoods (ESNs) in the European Union. • Synchronisation with EC Communication Activities: The goal is to become a highly visible showcase project for H2020. • High public visibility: there is major emphasis on addressing policy makers and cities. • Political inspiration by leading examples: GreenCharge aims to provide an easy to reference political example supported by implementing objectives of the EU Transport White Paper and the Urban Mobility Package (SUMP). • Increased reputation of EU funded projects: The aim of the communication strategy is to reach out to society, while demonstrating how EU funding is used to tackle societal challenges while generating business for (local) entrepreneurs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To maximise the impact of the GreenCharge project outcomes within and beyond its lifespan • To transfer the project results to relevant stakeholders (incl. policy makers, industry, and society) • To make sure that the technologies and business models developed in the project, and the lessons learned from the pilots, are made widely known and available to all relevant stakeholders • To facilitate effective project internal and external communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal Communications • External Communication

3 Impact Measurement

3.1 Approach and purpose

One of the first deliverables from GreenCharge was a detailed Communication Strategy and Plan (D8.1). Its purpose was to make sure that appropriate activities were undertaken to inform, engage, create awareness of and promote information about the project its aims, its funding source, and its outputs. There was an emphasis on communicating the wider societal and regulatory implications of GreenCharge, and their relevance to citizens.

Highlights of the GreenCharge approach were:

- Establish the GreenCharge “Brand” within the EU. We didn’t mean a brand in the sense of a consumer product, but rather a widely-known “household name” associated with a widely-supported positive goal. The GreenCharge brand should be synonymous with smart charging and ESNs.
- Synchronisation with EC Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Activities. GreenCharge co-operated actively in events and initiatives organised by the EC for promotion of H2020 activities. GreenCharge its goal was to become a highly visible showcase project for H2020.
- High public visibility. While GreenCharge addressed specialist and technical audiences, there was also a major emphasis on addressing policy makers and cities.
- Double role for communication. As in all projects, communication in GreenCharge was about promoting the project itself. But communication also had a second, and critical role: which is to positively influence the acceptance of eMobility, smart charging and ESNs.
- Political inspiration by leading examples for implementing objectives of the EU Transport White Paper and the Urban Mobility Package (SUMP).
- High emphasis on involvement from all partners All partners wanted to be actively involved in communication activities (and have PM budget allocated for this purpose), to emphasised the importance of the work, and to facilitated effective communication at the local level at all locations covered by the consortium.

3.2 Communication activities

The high impact communications activities that were carried out during the project are described in this section.

3.2.1 Website

A dedicated project website (see Figure 3-1) completely devoted to the GreenCharge project has been set up with a direct, simple and easy to remember URL, which reminds the acronym of the project: <https://www.greencharge2020.eu/>.

Figure 3-1: GreenCharge Website

The website provided a place where the open parts of the detailed knowledge generated in the project could be accessed directly by online users. This included project deliverables, detailed technical specifications, copies or links to scientific publications/conference proceedings, etc. It also provided information on how the project’s open research data can be accessed. The website will remain live after the project so that results continue to be available.

3.2.1.1 Impact of GreenCharge website

D8.1 Communication Strategy and Plan defined quantitative and qualitative KPIs to assess and measure communication impact. An initial summary of the website KPIs and their targets is shown in **Table 6**.

Table 6: Impact Measurement for the website of GreenCharge

Tools	KPI	Expected results	Actual result (Jan 2022)
Website	Number of unique visits	3,000	9,176
	Number of registered for upload	500	Not been registered during project
	Number of downloads of content	200	1,876, 4271 persons visited the page https://www.greencharge2020.eu/deliverables/ In total, 1,867 visitors downloaded one of the deliverables
	Number of subscribers for the newsletter	200	97 people are directly subscribed through the GreenCharge newsletter and GreenCharge has 1200/1500 subscribers though ICLEI
	Number of slots/articles:	12	10

Figure 3-2 shows the amount of website traffic (users) from September 2019 until January 2022. The figures shows peaks and they were linked to events (e.g. 9th Informed Cities in October 2021) or newsletters that were shared with the target audiences.

Figure 3-2 GreenCharge Website Traffic

German citizens were most interested in the website of GreenCharge

German citizens were most interested in the website of GreenCharge (13.75%) (see Figure 3-3). Citizens from the United States (10.01%) and India (7.4%) were also interested in the project. The number of the users is a bit lower; this is because it's not always possible to track from which country someone is browsing.

Figure 3-3 Geographic Population of GreenCharge Website Visitors

Figure 3-4 shows data produced by Google Analytics. This tool has been used for analyzing the data from the GreenCharge website. Results show on average session a visitor visited 2.36 pages and this took around 00:01:37. This means that on average users were actually searching for specific information (e.g. downloads for documents). This also means that visitors did not take the time to read the website for a long time. The amount of new users is around 10,057 and is actually higher than users 10,004. New users are users who have never been to your website, according to Google's tracking; users have visited your site before. The reason that there is a difference between the two numbers, is due to the Google Analytics metrics and could not be explained.

Figure 3-4 Statistics from the GreenCharge website (Google Analytics)

Acquisition (how do they reach the website)

Most visitors of GreenCharge website came through organic search, followed by direct traffic (people who type in the specific URL) and referral traffic (see Figure 3-5). This means that visitors reached out to the website through the search engine optimization (SEO) technique. This technique is the process of improving the quality and quantity of website traffic to a website or a web page from search engines. It aimed to improve the website's position in search results pages. SEO text means any type of text content on a website that utilizes search engine optimization techniques. It also includes files, like PDFs, which contains text that is optimized for search engines. The higher quality of the SEO-content (e.g. electrical vehicle/eMobility), the more people will find the website of GreenCharge on a search engine.

Top Channels

Figure 3-5 How visitors reach the GreenCharge Website

Behaviour (what do they do once they are on the website)

Figure 3-6 shows how visitors of the GreenCharge website behave. Most visitors entered through the homepage, followed by the article ‘What makes a charging system for electric vehicles smart?’. This article is performing well. This Figure is also attached as Appendix A.1 to this deliverable in order to make it better readable.

The article ‘Explaining the concepts of energy management, flexible charging and priority charging’ generated new visitors in recent months.

After the first pageview, most people go to the ‘about’ page, followed by ‘pilot overview’ and ‘deliverables’.

Figure 3-6 Behaviour of visitors on GreenCharge website

The most popular pages of the GreenCharge website from the start of the project up to January 2022 are (see Figure 3-7) (this Figure is also attached as Appendix A.2 to this deliverable in order to make it better readable):

1. Home page
2. About page
3. News: smart charging system electric vehicles

**/ is the homepage.*

Figure 3-7 GreenCharge website pages and data

3.2.2 Social Media

A social media grid was drawn that would plot the most appropriate social media channel/sites for targeting specific audiences. The intention was that this went using the media as just another way to “put out messages”. Social media was recognised as an opportunity to offers interaction with the wider community (people can e.g. respond to posts, re-tweet with remarks etc). Social media channels were actively monitored by project partners and used for dialogue with interested parties. This helped to create ‘communities of support’ for the project. We used techniques such as videos, animations, info-graphic imagery, mobile enabled content and richer content experiences.

3.2.2.1 Impact of GreenCharge social media channels

The graphic in Figure 3-8 below shows the follower growth from the start of the project until the 1st of January 2022. In total, at the 1st of November, GreenCharge has 236 followers on LinkedIn and 404 followers on Twitter. For both channels, the followers KPI is 200. At both LinkedIn and Twitter, the project has achieved the KPI of 200 followers.

Figure 3-8 Social Media Followers for LinkedIn & Twitter

LinkedIn

D8.1 Communication Strategy and Plan defined quantitative and qualitative KPIs to assess and measure communication impact. An initial summary of the LinkedIn KPIs and their targets is shown in **Table 7**.

Table 7: Impact Measurement for the LinkedIn of GreenCharge

Tools	KPI	Expected results	Actual result (Jan 2022)
LinkedIn	Number of followers	200	236
	Number of unique visits	200	271
	Number of posts	18	35

In October and November 2021 GreenCharge published a lot of content related to the Informed Cities Forum held on October 26th until 28th. We asked project partners to invite their network to follow the GreenCharge LinkedIn page. Due to Covid-19, there was a flattening amount of activity until August 2021 on social media. This meant that there were not much activities that were shared about the progress of the project.

Twitter

D8.1 Communication Strategy and Plan defined quantitative and qualitative KPIs to assess and measure communication impact. An initial summary of the Twitter KPIs and their targets is shown in **Table 8**.

Table 8: Impact Measurement for the Twitter of GreenCharge

Tools	KPI	Expected results	Actual result (Jan 2022)
Twitter	Number of Tweets	200	169
	Number of followers	200	404
	Number of retweets	50	258

GreenCharge posted 169 tweets during the project. This amount did not reach the KPI, but it certainly had impact since the number of followers and retweets were much higher in comparison with number of tweets.

Impressions on LinkedIn and Twitter

LinkedIn

Figure 3-9 Social Media Impression on LinkedIn

Figure 3-9 shows the number of impressions from January 2020 till January 2022. Impressions show the number of times each update is visible for at least 300 milliseconds with at least 50% in view on a (signed in) member's device screen or browser window (smartphone or computer). At Q4 2021 to the Informed Cities Forum in took place, which show the high frequency of impressions in comparison with the months before.

Figure 3-10 shows which posts had the most impressions:

Figure 3-10 Top Posts on Social Media Platform LinkedIn

Twitter

Figure 3-11 Social Media Impression on Twitter

Figure 3-11 shows the amount of impressions from the 1st of June until the 1st January 2022. GreenCharge generated more impressions on Twitter than LinkedIn. It seems that the GreenCharge target audience was more active on this platform. It is not possible to see which tweet generated the most impressions. But it was possible to see which tweets generated the most likes, retweets and replies. Figure 3-12 shows the tweets how had most retweets (and likes).

Figure 3-12 Top Tweets on Social Media Platform Twitter

3.2.3 Publications, press releases and newsletters

A press and media relations campaign was implemented, ensuring media interest and coverage from the outset of GreenCharge and throughout its duration. This has significantly raised public awareness and increased GreenCharge visibility. This section gives an overview of all publications, press releases and newsletters that GreenCharge delivered during the project.

3.2.3.1 Impact of GreenCharge publications, press releases and newsletters

D8.1 Communication Strategy and Plan defined quantitative and qualitative KPIs to assess and measure communication impact. An initial summary of the publications and press releases KPIs and their targets is shown in **Table 9**

Table 9: Impact Measurement for publications and press releases of GreenCharge

Tools	KPI	Expected results	Actual result (Jan 2022)
Press coverage	Number of EU wide press releases	8	10
	Number of slots/articles	12	15 (See Table 11: Describes the output for non-scientific publications of GreenCharge)
Publications	Number of newsletters	6	6 (The final newsletter will be published in February 2022)
	Number of scientific/technical publications	6	13
	Number of brochures spreaded	300	161 (Due to COVID-19)

Table 10 and Table 11 (next pages) give an overview of publications, press releases and newsletters that have been published during the projects lifetime.

Table 10: Describes the dissemination output for of GreenCharge

Title	Authors	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Peer reviewed (yes/no)	Is this a joint public/private publication? (yes/no)	Type of Publication	Open access? (yes-green-yes-gold, no).
Integrating e-mobility in smart energy neighborhoods ⁵	Rocco Aversa, Beniamino Di Martino, Salvatore Venticinque	Shaker Verlag	Conference Location: Garching (Munich), Germany	2018	yes		Chapter in Book	no
Evaluating Technology Innovation for e-Mobility ⁶	S. Venticinque, R. Aversa, B. Di Martino, M. Natvig, S. Jiang and R. E. Sard	IEEE	Conference Location: Napoli, Italy	2019	yes		Conference Publication	no
Stakeholder Motivation Analysis for Smart and Green Charging for Electric Mobility ⁷	Marit Natvig, Shanshan Jiang, Svein Hallsteinsen	Springer, Cham	Waina 2020	2020	yes	no	Conference paper	no
GreenCharge Simulation Tool ⁸	Aversa R., Branco D., Di Martino B., Venticinque S.	Springer, Cham	Conference Location: Caserta, Italy	2020	yes		Chapter in Book	no

⁵ Integrating e-mobility in smart energy neighborhoods (2018), url: <https://www.shaker.de/de/content/catalogue/index.asp?ISBN=978-3-8440-6138-3>

⁶ Evaluating Technology Innovation for e-Mobility (2019), url: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8795394>

⁷ Stakeholder Motivation Analysis for Smart and Green Charging for Electric Mobility(2020), url: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-3-030-44038-1_127

⁸ GreenCharge Simulation Tool (2020), url: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-3-030-44038-1_122

Title	Authors	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Peer reviewed (yes/no)	Is this a joint public/private publication? (yes/no)	Type of Publication	Open access? (yes-green-yes-gold, no).
An Event-Driven Multi Agent System for Scalable Traffic Optimization. ⁹	Horn, G., Przeździek, T., Büscher, M., Venticinque, S., Aversa, R., Di Martino, B., Esposito, A., Skrzypek, P., Leznik, M.,	Springer, Cham	Conference Location: Caserta, Italy	2020	yes		Chapter in Book	no
Tweets Analysis with Big Data Technology and Machine Learning to Evaluate Smart and Sustainable Urban Mobility Actions in Barcelona ¹⁰	Beniamino Di Martino, Luigi Colucci Cante, Mariangela Graziano, Regina Enrich Sard	Springer, Cham	Conference Location: Lodz (PL)	2021	yes		Chapter in Book	no
An Ontology Framework for Evaluating E-mobility Innovation ¹¹	Di Martino B., Colucci Cante L., Venticinque S.	Springer, Cham	Conference Location: Lodz (PL)	2021	yes		Chapter in Book	no
Semantic and knowledge based support to business model evaluation to stimulate green behaviour of electric	Beniamino Di Martino · Dario Branco · Luigi Colucci Cante · Salvatore Venticinque · Reinhard Scholten · Bas Bosma	Springer		2021	yes		Journal	yes-gold

⁹ An Event-Driven Multi Agent System for Scalable Traffic Optimization (2020), url: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-3-030-44038-1_125

¹⁰ Tweets Analysis with Big Data Technology and Machine Learning to Evaluate Smart and Sustainable Urban Mobility Actions in Barcelona (2021), url: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-3-030-50454-0_53

¹¹ An Ontology Framework for Evaluating E-mobility Innovation (2021), url: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-3-030-50454-0_54

Title	Authors	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Peer reviewed (yes/no)	Is this a joint public/private publication? (yes/no)	Type of Publication	Open access? (yes-green-yes-gold, no).
vehicles' drivers and energy prosumers ¹²								
Evaluation approach for smart charging ecosystem – with focus on automated data collection and indicator calculations ¹³	Marit K. Natvig, Shanshan Jiang, Svein Hallsteinsen, Salvatore Venticinque, Regina Enrich Sard	Springer	Toronto (Canada) – Online	2021	yes		Chapter in Book Series	no
A Big Data Analysis and Visualization Pipeline for Green ¹⁴ and Sustainable Mobility	Branco, D., Di Martino, B., Venticinque, S.	Springer	Toronto (Canada) – Online	2021	yes		Chapter in Book Series	no
Container Based Simulation of Electric Vehicles Charge Optimization ¹⁵	Aversa, R., Branco, D., Di Martino, B., Venticinque, S.	Springer	Toronto (Canada) – Online	2021	yes		Chapter in Book Series	no

¹²Semantic and knowledge based support to business model evaluation to stimulate green behaviour of electric vehicles' drivers and energy prosumers (2021), url: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007%2Fs12652-021-03243-4>

¹³ Evaluation approach for smart charging ecosystem – with focus on automated data collection and indicator calculations (2021), url: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-3-030-75078-7_65

¹⁴A Big Data Analysis and Visualization Pipeline for Green and Sustainable Mobility(2021), url: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-3-030-75078-7_69

¹⁵ Container Based Simulation of Electric Vehicles Charge Optimization (2021),url: https://parsec2.unicampania.it/venticinque/administrator/components/com_jresearch/files/publications/10_2021_aina_container_based.pdf

Title	Authors	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Peer reviewed (yes/no)	Is this a joint public/private publication? (yes/no)	Type of Publication	Open access? (yes-green-yes-gold, no).
Evaluation of innovative solutions for e-mobility ¹⁶	Venticinque, S., Di Martino, B., Aversa, R., Natvig, M.K., Jiang, S., Sard, R.E.	Inderscience		2021	yes		Journal	no
Lessons Learned from Demonstrating Smart and Green Charging in an Urban Living Lab ¹⁷	Shanshan Jiang, Marit Natvig, Svein Hallsteinsen, Karen Byskov Lindberg	Springer, Cham	Online	2022	yes		Conference paper	no

¹⁶ Evaluation of innovative solutions for e-mobility (2021), url: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-3-030-75078-7_13

¹⁷Lessons Learned from Demonstrating Smart and Green Charging in an Urban Living Lab(2022), url: <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/abs/10.1504/IJGUC.2021.114829>

Non-Scientific Publications

Table 11: Describes the output for non-scientific publications of GreenCharge

<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors or Partners</i>	<i>Title of the journal</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Type of Publication</i>	<i>Link to the publication</i>
Ectromobility-focused project kicked off in Trondheim (Norway).	PNO	CIVITAS website News	18.01 .2019	Blog entry	https://civitas.eu/news/greencharge-project-go
Business models for sustainable electric vehicle charging solutions	PNO	Open Access Government	01.01 .2020	Non-scientific publication	https://edition.pagesuite-professional.co.uk/Launch.aspx?EID=e7e65f16-14bb-415e-a4a7-84c443d8db40
Norske forskere skal designe fremtidens elbil-samfunn	SINTEF	Forskning.no	05.02 .2018	Blog entry	https://forskning.no/transport-sintef/norske-forskere-skal-designe-fremtidens-elbil-samfunn/1121439
E-mobility/SUMPs	BRE MEN	GreenCharge project website	17.06 .2019	Non-scientific publication	https://www.greencharge2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/leaflet_GreenCharge_e-mobility_and_SUMP.pdf
Business model innovation	PNO	GreenCharge project website	06.12 .2019	Blog entry	https://www.greencharge2020.eu/news/the-generation-game/
Business model innovation	PNO	GreenCharge project website	07.01 .2020	Blog entry	https://www.greencharge2020.eu/news/introduction-business-model-processes/
Smart charging concept	PNO	GreenCharge project website	14.01 .2020	Blog entry	https://www.greencharge2020.eu/news/smart-charging-system-electric-vehicles/
Stimulating e-mobility	PNO	GreenCharge project website	04.02 .2020	Blog entry	https://www.greencharge2020.eu/news/make-electric-driving-success/
Energy management and smart charging	PNO	GreenCharge project website	17.03 .2020	Blog entry	https://www.greencharge2020.eu/news/energy-management-flexible-charging-priority-charging/
GreenCharge's pilots	PNO	CIVITAS website News	13.12 .2019	Blog entry	https://civitas.eu/news/e-mobility-makes-great-strides-greencharge-cities
INEA Urban Mobility Brochure 2019	PNO	INEA Website	01.10 .2019	Non-scientific publication	https://ec.europa.eu/inea/sites/inea/files/urban_mobility_brochure_2019_web.pdf
Clean, smart and efficient electric mobility	ICLEI	Transportation-as-a-Service magazine	01.07 .2020	Non-scientific publication	https://publishing.ninja/V4/page/10637/414/270/1

Project overview	PNO	Consultancy.eu	21.10.2020	Blog entry	https://www.consultancy.eu/news/5072/pno-consultants-supporting-greencharge-project-in-three-cities
Oslo pilot (in Japanese)	Select Partner	NIKKEI	6.10.2021	Non-scientific publication	https://www.nikkei.com/article/DGXZQOGR210AK0R20C21A9000000/?gift=g21s5hXtuLqjg5OTM1NDcxMjikNkZRea3mt7HlsL4g5bm455SfMgE.xOeo2T-h
Innlegg: Smart teknologi vil krympe ladekostnader og redusere behovet for dyr nettutbygging	SINTEF	Dagens Næringsliv (DN)	18-12-2021	Non-scientific publication	https://www.dn.no/innlegg/klimateknologi/innlegg-smart-teknologi-vil-krympe-ladekostnader-og-reducere-behovet-for-dyr-nettutbygging/2-1-1104754

Newsletters

News and updates of the project were distributed through newsletters. The aim was to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly informed about the latest project’s developments. Six newsletters were issued, two newsletters per year, and distributed across Europe to an existing and further enlarged mailing list of 200+ recipients from local government, academia, business, NGOs and other relevant stakeholders, which made use of the already established e-newsletter 'Informed Cities' (heritage of the FP7 project PRIMUS), as well as to all other project partners' dissemination channels.

Newsletter Audience and Concept

The newsletters contained meaningful content for professionals as well as assisting in promoting the GreenCharge project. The newsletter did not focus on experts in the field but did focus on building a general understanding and acceptance of e-mobility, priming actors which were more involved in this field in the future (such as those involved in transport planning but without detailed e-mobility plans) as well as others in adjoining sectors (such as building and planning) who could be more involved in enabling the effective delivery of e-mobility measures if their overall knowledge and competence in the field was greater.

For detailed and complex project findings and information, the newsletter referred to deliverables hosted on the website and other sources of information. The newsletter itself was not intended to be a technical document,

Figure 3-13 gives an overview of the newsletters that were published during GreenCharge (the final GreenCharge newsletter will be published end of February 2022).

Figure 3-13 GreenCharge Newsletters (2019-2021)

3.2.3.2 Impact of the GreenCharge Newsletter

In the first year of the project the first two newsletters were published. These newsletters were produced and distributed electronically to about 1500+ recipients. This was done by making use of the Informed Cities Newsletter, in which GreenCharge is heavily profiled (alongside other mobility projects). In this Informed Cities Newsletter there was a click-through to the separate and subordinate GreenCharge newsletter which was branded separately and contains a fuller range of stories dedicated to GreenCharge. In the first Informed Cities Newsletter, GreenCharge was given a significant headline slot¹⁸.

It was proposed that as far as possible, each WP gave a headline article slot in one of the six newsletters. The main themes of each of the six newsletters are shown in Table 12. The already published newsletters can be found under the hyperlinks, which are located in the footnotes.

¹⁸ <https://mailchi.mp/ce3326bd0844/newsletternov2018-461737>

Table 12: Newsletter themes and dates of publication

Newsletter number	Focus theme	WP focus	Foreword author	Date of publication ¹⁹
1.	Pilot cities ²⁰	WP2	Joe Gorman (SINTEF)	February 2019
2.	Business models and prototypes for cities ²¹	WP3	Arno Schoevaars (PNO Consultants)	October 2019
3.	Evaluation of measures ²²	WP5	Beniamino di Martino (University of Campania Luigi Vanvitelli)	March 2020
4.	EV roaming ²³	WP4	Jürgen Werneke & Arjun Subramanian (Hsubject)	September 2020
5.	Reference Architecture ²⁴	WP4	Shanshan Jiang (SINTEF)	September 2021
6.	Summary and goodbye	WP1	Jacqueline Floch (SINTEF)	February 2022

In addition to GreenCharge’s separate newsletter and its coverage in the Informed Cities Newsletter, the project has also been mentioned in the CIVITAS MOVE newsletter from January 2019²⁵.

3.2.4 Events

The COVID-19 pandemic affected the implementation of the GreenCharge events and attendance of external events. Due to the pandemic it was not possible to have physical events. Therefore most of the activities took place through the ethernet, which GreenCharge embraced. This means that events as discussed in Table 14 still took place through various digital applications (e.g. YouTube/Microsoft Teams/Zoom etc.), including the final conference²⁶. GreenCharge was involved in the arrangement of two other events such as a dedicated SUMP workshop in Bremen and a workshop at the ICNC (International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications) Conference.

Again, several external events were planned during the lifetime of GreenCharge. This included self-organised events like workshops, a GreenCharge conference, webinars and open days. Also, the GreenCharge project was presented at various external events in the mobility sector. GreenCharge ensured that results were communicated at relevant international conferences/workshops. The project presented the SUMP approach at city-related events of the EC like CIVITAS Forum, Transport Research Arena (TRA) etc. In addition, relevant industrial/interest group events were used.

GreenCharge partners self-organised several events of different types. This included a GreenCharge conference, workshops, open days and webinars. A description of the type of conferences is summarised below:

GreenCharge conference. During year 3 of the GreenCharge project, a larger (approx. 150 participants) 1.5-day Informed Cities conference was envisaged to convene project partners and Uptake Cities with a cross-European mix of participants from local government, academia, business, NGOs and other organisations,

¹⁹ These are provisional dates. Exact dates to be confirmed.

²⁰ <https://www.greencharge2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/GreenCharge-Newsletter-February-2019.pdf>

²¹ <https://www.greencharge2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Green-Charge-Newsletter-October-2019.pdf>

²² <https://www.greencharge2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Green-Charge-Newsletter-3.pdf>

²³ <https://www.greencharge2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Green-Charge-Newsletter-4-September.pdf>

²⁴ <https://www.greencharge2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Green-Charge-Newsletter-5-final.pdf>

²⁵ [https://mailchi.mp/civitas/civitas-move-newsletter-35?e=\[UNIQID\]](https://mailchi.mp/civitas/civitas-move-newsletter-35?e=[UNIQID])

²⁶ <https://www.greencharge2020.eu/event/9th-informed-cities-forum-to-cast-light-on-electric-mobility-and-cultural-heritage/>

shared and contested the project outcomes. This was done by the coordinator ICLEI, the consortium dedicated one edition (the 9th Edition) of the established conference series 'Informed Cities' to the GreenCharge project. ICLEI co-developed the programme together with the project partners, involving also other relevant experts working in the same thematic area. Prevailing COVID conditions and prudent risk management meant on-site audience participation was not made possible, however a key core group of GreenCharge partners including the Coordinator and Innovation Manager gathered on-site to provide an online event. All sessions were recorded, and in addition to the real time viewers these are gathering additional viewers online (e.g. approaching 250 views of “The future of mobility: Which electric vehicle fairy tale will you fall in love with?” at the time of writing). The dedicated video playlist will be maintained on the ICLEI Europe YouTube channel²⁷ following the end of GreenCharge to ensure an ongoing legacy for the event and the knowledge created, discussed and communicated.

Workshops were planned to develop business models in Bremen, Barcelona and Oslo. In addition, a workshop at the ICNC (International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications) Conference was planned.

Open days. The project plenary meetings were arranged approximately every 8 months, each lasting 3-4 days. These were primarily intended for coordination of work within the consortium itself. Once a year, one full day of such meetings was designated as the “open day”. A selected group of external stakeholders was invited to each open day; some time was used for presentation of the project, but most time was used for an open dialogue between the consortium partners and the external stakeholders. The presence of most key members of the project allowed the arrangement of detailed one-to-one discussions on specific topics on an ad hoc basis.

Webinars. GreenCharge held at least 5 (Uptake Cities) webinars during the project duration at M12, M21, M30, M36 and M42. These were 30-40-minute talks by 1-2 members of the consortium on project topics. This was followed by 20-30 minutes of questions and answers by attendees. Some of these webinars have been recorded and uploaded to the project’s website to YouTube, Vimeo etc. (not all webinars were uploaded since these primarily served for guiding the Uptake Cities through the process of making their own e-mobility roadmap).

3.2.4.1 Impact of the GreenCharge events

D8.1 Communication Strategy and Plan defined quantitative and qualitative KPIs to assess and measure communication impact. An initial summary of the publications and press releases KPIs and their targets is shown in **Table 13**.

Table 13: Impact Measurement for the events of GreenCharge

Tools	KPI	Expected results	Actual results
Events	Number of large-scale events	1	7 (See Table 14 for more details)
	Number of workshops	9	23
	Number of open days	3	1
	Number of conferences	20	25

²⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h5H9cvloMAU&list=PLv-mhCFisOsXBFxpU1UpELWBgx3KfnuIU>

Table 14 Table 15: gives an of overview of events where GreenCharge attended, press releases and newsletters have been published during GreenCharge.

Table 14: Events attended by GreenCharge partners

No.	Participation date from	Partner	Event	Location	Type of event	Dissemination action	Target audience	Size of audience	Countries addressed
1	Sep-18	SUN	32nd EnviroInfo-2018 conference, Environmental Informatics Techniques and Trends	Garching (Munich)	Conference (Participation)	Oral presentation	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		
2	Nov-18	SINTEF	SINTEF Mobility Workshop	Trondheim, Norway	Workshop (Participation)	Oral presentation	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	60	All
3	Nov-18	SINTEF	Smart City Expo Congress	Barcelona, Spain	Conference (Participation)	Oral presentation	Select targeted audiences	250	
4	Nov-18	PNO	GreenCharge workshop	Oslo, Norway	Workshop (Organisation)	Targeted seminars/meetings	Other	25	Norway
5	Nov-18	PNO	GreenCharge workshop	Barcelona, Spain	Workshop (Organisation)	Targeted seminars/meetings	Other	25	Spain
6	Dec-18	PNO	GreenCharge workshop	Bremen, Germany	Workshop (Organisation)	Targeted seminars/meetings	Other	25	Germany
7	Feb-19	SINTEF	Information exchange between GreenCharge and HZ 2020 lighthouse project + CityXchange	Trondheim, Norway	Other	Oral presentation	Other	1	Norway
8	Mar-19	ICLEI	Uptake City Group - Internal workshop	Barcelona, Spain	Workshop (Organisation)	Oral presentation	Other		
9	Apr-19	Hubject PNO	GreenCharge workshop	Berlin, Germany	Workshop (Organisation)	Targeted seminars/meetings	Other	5	
10	May-19	PMC PNO	GreenCharge workshop	Bremen, Germany	Workshop (Organisation)	Targeted seminars/meetings	Select targeted audiences	5	Germany

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11	Jun-19	PNO	Clean energy, clean mobility” – EV ENERGY final conference	Almere, The Netherlands	Conference (Participation)	Roll-up	Policy Makers	80	EU: main countries attending NL, SE, UK, FR, ES (Barcelona)
12	Jun-19	PNO	ITS European Congress	Brainport, The Netherlands	Conference (Participation)	Roll-up	Industry		
13	Jun-19	SUN	IEEE 28th International Conference on Enabling Technologies: Infrastructure for Collaborative Enterprises (WETICE),	Naples, Italy	Conference (Participation)	Oral presentation	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		
14	Jun-19	Bremen ICLEI, SINTEF	6th European Conference on SUMP	Groningen, The Netherlands	Conference (Participation)	Brochures	Policy Makers	500	EU
15	Jun-19	BREMEN	North Sea Climate Conference	Marstrand, Sweden	Conference (Participation)	Oral presentation	Policy Makers	200	
16	Sep-19	SINTEF	Norwegian Solar Energy Day	Oslo, Norway	Conference (Participation)	Oral presentation		160-180	
17	Oct-19	PNO, BREMEN, SINTEF ICLEI	CIVITAS Forum	Graz, Austria	Exhibition	Brochures	Policy Makers		
18	Oct-19	ICLEI	Uptake Cities Bremen study visit	Bremen, Germany	Other	Oral presentation	Policy Makers		
19	Oct-19	ICLEI	G20 Transport Task Force	Tokyo, Japan	Brokerage Event	Oral presentation	Policy Makers	30	G20 Group
20	Nov-19	MOTIT	Smart City Expo World Congress	Barcelona, Spain	Conference (Participation)	Roll-up	Select targeted audiences		
21	Nov-20	MOTIT	2nd Forum for Electric, Connected & Autonomous Vehicle, Spain - China	Madrid, Spain	Brokerage Event		Industry		Spain, China
22	Jan-20	SINTEF, ESMART + OSLO	Oslo Pilot Launch	Oslo, Norway	Open days	Oral presentation	General Public		

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23	Feb-20	HUBJ	E-World Energy & Water	Essen, Germany	Trade Fair	Roll-up	Industry		
24	Sep-20	PNO	European EV Charging Summit 2020	Rotterdam, (NL)	Conference (Participation)	Oral presentation	Industry	20	Europe
25	Sep-20	SINTEF	Nordic Edge Expo	Digital	Exhibition	Video	Policy Makers		
26	Oct-20	SINTEF	Sustainable places	Digital	eMOBILITY workshop	Oral presentation			
27	Sep-20	ICLEI	European Sustainable Cities and Towns (ESTC) Conference	Mannheim, Germany	Conference (Organisation)	-	Targeted seminars/meetings	Policy Makers	1000
28	Sep-20	ICLEI	European Mobility Days - N.B. there is an overlap with the ESCT conference above.	Brussels, Belgium	Conference (Participation)	?	Oral presentation	Policy Makers	1000
29	Oct-20	ICLEI	Electric Mobility and Renewables in Action Plans	Digital	Webinar	Free	Will mention GC in online chat	Local authorities	
30	Oct-20	ICLEI	Boosting Clean e-mobility in Europe	Digital	Webinar	Free	Will mention GC in online chat	Local authorities	
31	Oct-20	SINTEF	Evaluation Impact Workshop (CIVITAS)	Digital	Workshop (Participation)	Free	Targeted seminars/meetings	Other	
32	Oct-20	SINTEF	CIVITAS ELEVATE - ECG Meeting	Digital	Workshop (Participation)	Presentation	Other CIVITAS projects	Select targeted audiences	10?
33	Mar-21	SINTEF	CIVITAS ELEVATE - ECG Meeting	Digital	Workshop (Participation)	Oral presentation	Other CIVITAS projects	Select targeted audiences	10?
34	Jun-21	SINTEF	SINTEF/ ITL innovation seminar	Digital	Brokerage Event	Oral presentation	Estonian Association of Information Technology and Telecommunications	Select targeted audiences	1
35	Jun-21	SINTEF	CIVITAS ELEVATE 3dr ECG Meeting	Digital	Workshop (Participation)	Presentation	Other CIVITAS projects	Select targeted audiences	10?

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	Oct-21	SINTEF Bremen	Testing innovative business models in electromobility in cities: experiences in a zero-emission transport system from European and CIVITAS projects @MEISTER_H2020 & @GreenCharge2020	Aachen	Workshop (Participation)	Presentation	Other CIVITAS projects	500	30
37	Nov-21	ATLANTIS	MeetUp publicoprivat: impulsa la promoció econòmica amb la mobilitat	Barcelona	Workshop (Participation)	Presentation	Municipalities from Barcelona Metropolitan area	35	

Webinars. GreenCharge gave 7 webinars during the project duration. The COVID-19 situation has pushed partners to be more active online and that is why webinars were done more extensively, for more details see Table 15.

Table 15: Webinars during GreenCharge

Specific presentations at events					
Date	Title	Event	Location	Author	Partner
Sep 2019	This is GreenCharge ²⁸	Webinar programme	Online	Reggie Tricker	ICLEI Europe
June 2020	Roadmap to e-mobility ²⁹			Reggie Tricker	ICLEI Europe
March 2021	This town aint big enough for the two of us			Paal Mork	City of Oslo
March 2021	Bremen’s Challenges			Beate Lange	City of Bremen
March 2021	Kerbside Parking Management for electric mobility			Multiple	Uptake Cities Group
Sept 2021	Business model design – the role of cities			Bas, Bosma, Maurits Simons	EGEN
Sep 2021	Roll-out charging infrastructure – The German way			Beate Lange	City of Bremen

3.2.5 Lectures for students and academics

The Università degli Studi della Campania Luigi Vanvitelli (SUN) is interested in project results related to their own students. The results of GreenCharge were immediately exploited during lectures by involving master students on project related topics, and on the topics taught in the course *INF5870 - Energy Informatics covering computing and communications technologies and their applications for sustainable energy sectors - e.g., smart grid, solar, electric vehicles, and storage*. This course lay the foundations to understand where and how computer engineering techniques were applied in the energy systems.

3.2.6 Animation video about GreenCharge

An animated video was developed during the GreenCharge project. At the end of 2020, this animation was published on YouTube and promoted through the website and social media channels GreenCharge. The creation of a movie/animation is a perfect way of visualising the GreenCharge project and making it understandable in a quick way. It helped to share the GreenCharge concept for a broader audience. The project [video³⁰](#) is finished and uploaded on the 7th of December 2020.

²⁸ <https://www.greencharge2020.eu/news/greencharge-webinar-available/>

²⁹ https://www.greencharge2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/GreenCharge_Uptake-Cities-Report-Webinar-2.pdf

³⁰ Youtube (2020) GreenCharge Project Video, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=2iBXLf1CvEo>

Figure 3-14: YouTube Video of GreenCharge H2020

3.2.6.1 Impact of animation video GreenCharge

YouTube

Table 16: Impact Measurement for the YouTube Animation Video of GreenCharge

Tools	KPI	Expected results	Actual results
YouTube	Number of project videos	1	1
	Number of webinars	3	7
	Number of views	500	1,010 291 views – GreenCharge Video 719 views 9 th Informed Cities Forum ³¹
	Number of subscribers	50	1 ³²

The GreenCharge YouTube video itself did not reach the number of views (291). However, the GreenCharge concept was shared through video playlist of 9th Informed Cities forum which had 719 views.

The GreenCharge YouTube account has currently one subscriber. This is not surprising since GreenCharge does not regularly create and post video content. To gain visibility and gain subscribers, you need to post more and continuously.

3.2.7 Informed Cities/ Final Conference

The 9th Informed Cities Forum³³ "Re-purpose. Re-charge. Re-think. Heritage and e-mobility at the crossroads" took place online on 26-28 October 2021 and connected urban dreamers, thinkers and doers from two worlds:

³¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h5H9cvloMAU&list=PLv-mhCFisOsXBFXpU1UpELWBgx3KfnuIU>

³² <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCrzcNKhFs8tlQnVa3vgcJDw>

³³ <https://informedcities.eu/events/9th-informed-cities-forum/>

from the worlds of cultural heritage and electric mobility. The goal was to bridge the gap between these two seemingly unrelated topics, collectively search for links and connections between them, provoke discussions that normally wouldn't take place and break the silos.

So what do cultural heritage and electric mobility have in common? Think of heritage sites adopting e-mobility solutions, like electric mini-trams, electric vans, and e-bike or e-scooter sharing schemes, to make places of culture more accessible with possibly minimal environmental impact. Think of EV charging stations popping up in our cities and becoming a new element of the urban landscapes. Eventually, think of the role mobility plays in culture and how the electrification of our vehicles will shape this role in the future. Will urban communities have to become more open to collaborating, sharing, and trusting one another? Will “re-purpose, re-charge, and re-think” define how our future cities look like?

At the 9th Informed Cities Forum there were no right and wrong answers, and sometimes there were no answers at all. The goal was to find a common language, collectively explore both topics and bring them together, or at least closer to one another.

The 9th Informed Cities was co-organised by the GreenCharge, and OpenHeritage projects, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

3.2.7.1 Impact of Informed Cities Final Conference on GreenCharge

Table 17: Impact Measurement for the Informed Cities and final conference of GreenCharge

Tools	KPI	Expected results	Results
Networks	Number of uptake cities	12	8
	Number of reference groups	3	3
	Number of actors accessible through partner networks	469	GreenCharge did not measure the number of actors accessible through partner networks. Therefore, this actual result is not applicable anymore and will not part in the final reporting.

The number of uptake cities reaching the final stage of producing a roadmap was 8. GreenCharge did not complete the whole programme with 12 cities and this could be ascribed to the lack of direct financial incentives uptake cities had available for staff time from the project, the reduced offer in terms of site visits due to COVID restrictions which limited the attraction of the learning programme, limited direct perceived relevance of the technological solutions to direct partner contacts (involved in planning), and in one instance unfortunately the passing of the representative involved in the project. In order to fill the vacant slots, awareness was raised with cities in newsletters and social media. It is felt that the enthusiastic participation of the 8 cities that did attend allowed a deeper level and higher quality of engagement and outweighed having higher numbers.

Local Reference Groups (LRG), at each pilot site, were recruited among relevant stakeholders (citizens and businesses in ESN, city representatives, interest groups, etc.). They were actively involved through for example business model workshops, surveys, interviews, etc. to provide input to needs, requirements and feedbacks for the project development, evaluation and exploitation.

The conference report³⁴ (Figure 3-15) documents the 9th Informed Cities Forum by highlighting key outcomes and discussions from the event. Moreover, the communication outcomes of this event is summarized in Figure 3-16.

³⁴ https://informedcities.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/9th-Informed-Cities-report.pdf

Figure 3-15: Informed Cities Forum Report

Figure 3-16: Output from Informed Cities #9

3.3 Summary table

Table 18 (see next page) gives an overview of the agreed KPI's and the output realized through the communication activities.

Table 18: Impact Measurement of Key Performance Indicators

Tools	KPI	Expected results	Realized results	KPI Reached
Website	Number of unique visits	3,000	9,176 (KPI reached)	Yes
	Number of registered for upload	500	Not been registered during project	No
	Number of downloads of content	200	1,876 4271 persons visited the page https://www.greencharge2020.eu/deliverables/ . In total, 1867 visitors downloaded one of the deliverables	Yes
	Number of subscribers for the newsletter	200	97 people are directly subscribed through the GreenCharge newsletter and GreenCharge has 1200/1500 subscribers through ICLEI	Yes
Press coverage	Number of EU wide press releases	8	10	Yes
	Number of slots/articles	12	15	Yes
Publications	Number of newsletters	6	6	Yes
	Number of scientific/technical publications	6	12	Yes
	Number of brochures spreaded	300	5	No
Twitter	Number of Tweets	200	169	No
	Number of followers	200	404	Yes
	Number of retweets	50	258	Yes
LinkedIn	Number of followers	200	236	Yes
	Number of unique visits	200	271	Yes
	Number of posts	18	35	Yes
YouTube	Number of project videos	1	1	Yes
	Number of webinars	3	7	Yes
	Number of views	500	1.010	Yes
	Number of subscribers	50	1	No
Networks	Number of uptake cities	12	8	No
	Number of reference groups	3	3	Yes
	Number of actors accessible through partner networks	469	Not been measured during GreenCharge	No
Events	Number of large-scale events	1	7 (Events >100 audience size)	Yes
	Number of workshops	9	23	Yes
	Number of open days	3	1 (Due to COVID-19)	No
	Number of conferences	20	25	Yes

3.3.1 Introduction and description of the table

D8.1 Communication Strategy and Plan defined quantitative and qualitative targets to assess and measure communication impact. Table 18 was updated during this deliverable by adding the results of the project, see last column Table 18.

3.3.2 Evaluation of the communication results

The quantitative results are shown in Figure 3-17. This figure **shows that 76% of the developed KPIs were reached during the project.** The explanation of the various activities are described in the next section: Explanation of the communication results.

Figure 3-17 High Impact Communication KPI Results - GreenCharge

3.3.3 Explanation of the communication results

Website, 75% of the KPIs were reached. The latter who were reached was due to the fact that this KPI's was not registered during the project. No one within the GreenCharge project could explain what was meant here.

Press Coverage, 100% of the KPIs were reached. The project itself had even more EU wide press releases (>25%) and number of slots/articles (25%).

Publications, 66% of the KPIs were reached. The amount of publications was doubles during the period, but the 33% who were not reached were due to the COVID-19 pandemic. It was not possible to organise and go to physical events. This affected the *number of brochures spreaded*, because it was not possible to do this in the digital environment.

Social Media (Twitter and LinkedIn), 83% of the KPIs were reached. The only KPI who was not reached was the number of Tweets for Twitter. The reason for this had to do with fact that there were less physical events due to the COVID-19 pandemic. A lot of events were cancelled and therefore it was not possible to communicate about it. However, GreenCharge still reached 404 followers (>202%) and had 258 (>516%). number of retweets. This means that GreenCharge actively involved in discussion about EV mobility. The amount of followers on LinkedIn was 18% more that was described in D8.1 The reason for this has probably to do with the fact that GreenCharge was more active on LinkedIn. The LinkedIn page posted 98% more than was described at the beginning of the project.

YouTube, 75% of the KPIs were reached. The 25% that GreenCharge did not reach was the amount of subscribers at the YouTube channels. This was mainly due to the fact that there was one main project video. This did not attract enough people to engage with the GreenCharge YouTube Channel.

Networks, 33% of the KPIs were reached. This was due to the number of Uptake cities. This was lower than expected (<33%) and was due to the pandemic. The high uncertainty of the pandemic has led that there were less number of uptake cities. The other KPI that did not reach was the *number of actors accessible through partner networks*. This KPI was not measured during the GreenCharge project and therefore there is no result.

Events, 75% of the KPIs were reached. The number of open days did not meet its KPI due to the pandemic. The amount of large scale events, workshops and conferences was much greater. This was mainly due to the fact that the events went digital. Most of the events still took place through digital solutions that GreenCharge partners embraced. This means that activities as discussed still took place through various digital channels (e.g. YouTube/Microsoft Teams/Zoom and other digital tools).

4 Conclusions

The document describes the measures proposed by the GreenCharge Consortium to effectively communicate project's activities and results during the lifetime of the project.

This deliverable reports on the impact of the communication activities. Focus is on high impact communication and this covers website, social media, newsletters and publications, conferences, workshops, lectures to students and animation. As such this deliverable gives a valuable overview of how GreenCharge's results that have been communicated, but also presented their impact on interested stakeholders.

Different communication channels were selected to efficiently address the different target groups derived from a stakeholder analysis at the beginning of the project. This ensured in effective community building and spreading the results of the GreenCharge project. Moreover, collaboration with other initiatives such as *CIVITAS Initiatives & Uptake Cities* helped to achieve more engagement with potential stakeholders. These stakeholders were reached by the participation of partners. This was required to maximize the impact and visibility of the GreenCharge project.

The activities that were planned in advance the project were necessary to align operations and to ensure the engagement of the stakeholder community. Branding and image were important to make the GreenCharge project recognizable and rememberability of the GreenCharge Project. Each partner included this branding within their communication activities.

As the project evolved, GreenCharge refined its Communication Strategy and Plan. This was due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This affected the implementation of the GreenCharge demonstrators and the communication activities, especially the physical activities. Nonetheless, the project still achieved 76% of the agreed KPIs of the High Impact Communication Report. GreenCharge is very proud of the HIC results, because the pandemic and social distancing did not help to run a normal project. Most of the activities went through the ethernet and all the available applications that enabled to partners to communicate (e.g. YouTube/Microsoft Teams/Zoom and other digital tools).

In this way GreenCharge was able to:

- Established a GreenCharge "Brand" within the EU which acted as a reference for smart charging and Energy Smart Neighborhoods in the European Union.
- Synchronized with EC Communication Activities and visible showcase project for H2020.
- Have a high public and online visibility, due to incorporation of digital solutions and the emphasis on addressing EU policy makers and cities.
- Political inspiration by providing an easy to reference political example supported by implementing objectives of the EU Transport White Paper and the Urban Mobility Package (SUMP).
- Increased the reputation of EU funded projects which demonstrated, even during the COVID-19 pandemic, how EU funding is used to tackle societal challenges while generating business for (local) entrepreneurs.

Appendix A

A.1 – Behaviour of GreenCharge’s website visitors

A.2 - GreenCharge’s website data and page visitors

			31,559 % of Total: 100.00% (31,559)	31,559 % of Total: 100.00% (31,559)
<input type="checkbox"/>	1. /		7,547	23.91%
<input type="checkbox"/>	2. /about-project/		4,039	12.80%
<input type="checkbox"/>	3. /news/smart-charging-system-electric-vehicles/		2,580	8.18%
<input type="checkbox"/>	4. /deliverables/		2,404	7.62%
<input type="checkbox"/>	5. /pilot-overview/		1,932	6.12%
<input type="checkbox"/>	6. /news/		1,107	3.51%
<input type="checkbox"/>	7. /contact/		841	2.66%
<input type="checkbox"/>	8. /consortium/		754	2.39%
<input type="checkbox"/>	9. /deliverables/data-management-plan/		744	2.36%
<input type="checkbox"/>	10. /news/energy-management-flexible-charging-priority-charging/		469	1.49%

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